

A STUDY ON PREPARATION, FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF LIP PEEL OFF FROM JUICE EXTRACT.

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ABSTRACT:

Over the past few years, lipsticks have been used as a potent cosmetic that can improve one's own appearance and confidence. But the synthetic colors used in the lipsticks are more harmful and can cause serious adverse effects. Because of that, natural and herbal formulation are thought to be safer and have fewer side effects than synthetic ones, hence they are more widely accepted throughout the world. The present article is based on herbal formulation as we have developed an lip peel-off and assessed it for various evaluation parameters like spreadability, irritancy, folding endurance and proved that Lip peel off formulation exhibits higher comparability and no irritant effects and also excellent stability at room temperature and flow characteristics. This lip peel off is used for cleansing, moisturizing and also help in removing the dead skin cells. Moreover it peels like an elastic membrane and this peel-off has been used for the benefit of being practical.

Key words: Lip peel, Gelatin, Aloe vera, Beetroot, Juice extract, Formulation.

INTRODUCTION:

The lips are an essential part of the human face which is responsible for intimacy, phonation, sensation, mastication, facial expression, and physical appearance. Labium superius oris refers to the upper lip, whereas Labium inferius oris refers to the lower lip. The top and lower lips each have cutaneous surfaces, vermilion, and mucosal membranes. Lip size and colour have been associated with sentiments of attraction. The proverb "red lipstick mimics vasodilation which renders more attractive" may have its origins in evolution and explains why lipstick has become so popular. ^[1]

Lipstick has long been regarded as a powerful cosmetic that can boost self-esteem and beauty. Whether it's a delicate nude or a bold red, lipstick can finish the overall makeup look and make you feel like a million bucks. Not only does lipstick look nice, but it also boost one's confidence. ^[2]

According to a study undertaken by the University of California, Berkeley School of Public Health, the majority of lip glosses and lipsticks on the market today contain dangerously high quantities of cadmium, lead, aluminium, and chromium, among other toxic substances. The study also found that continuous exposure to these levels could lead to long-term health concerns, particularly in people who use lipstick more than twice or three times in a 24-hour period. Likewise, frequent use raises the risk of chromium excess, which has been linked to the development of abdominal cancer. Other harmful ingredients discovered in lipsticks:

- The endocrine system is harmed by phthalates.
- Lead exposure raises a number of long-term health concerns.
- Lipstick frequently contains parabens, which are skin-penetrating chemicals. They have been linked to a number of negative effects, such as diarrhoea and depression. ^[3]
- Peel-off masks are distinguished by the use of film-forming polymers, which, when fully dried, generate an exceptionally cohesive plastic layer, allowing the product to be removed manually without leaving any trace. Furthermore, it has a little moisturizing effect and increases the epithelium's reactivity to active chemicals, especially due to the occlusive behavior of the plastic polymeric layer. Peel-off masks gently remove the facial skin's outermost layer, reducing dullness and dead skin. This can help to regulate pigmentation while also smoothing the skin's texture. Peel-off masks are helpful to clear pores and diminish fine lines. ^[4]

Beet root juice is a natural colorant that ranges from bright red to purple. Beet root comprises of water-soluble pigments known as betalains. They are found in the vacuole juice of beet root cells and are easily released when the cells are damaged. Betalains are a class of pigments whose colors range from yellow to orange to reddish-purple. The total betalains in fresh beet juice are around 1g/lit (0.1%). The most common of them is red-colored betanin, sometimes known as "beetroot red," which gives beet root juice its distinguishing purple-red color. ^[5]

Based on the context of the mentioned problem, herbal cosmetics are less common than synthetic cosmetics in terms of negative impacts. Herbal ingredients are suitable for all skin types.

The lips peel-off is used to colour the lips and improve their appearance. It is also used to cleanse, moisturize and to remove dead skin. It is created by combining polymers that can produce a thin coating on the skin. The lips peel off mask is placed as a thin film and distributed with fingers on the lips. It is allowed to dry before being gently removed from the lips with fingertips.

The objective of this study is to develop and evaluate a lips peel-off formulation containing herbal ingredients, such as extraction of Beetroot juice, *Aloe barbadensis*, gelatine, Poly Vinyl Alcohol (PVA) and so on.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The formulation constituents, such as Beetroot, Orange peel, *Aloe barbadensis*, PVA (polyvinyl alcohol), gelatine and citric acid, were purchased at a local market and also collected from a medicinal garden. The details of all ingredients used in formulation are mentioned below;

Fig no 1: Ingredients used in the Formulation

- a) **Beetroot extraction:** Beetroot is washed to remove dirt and cut into small pieces and grind in mixer, then it is squeezed to extract juice. The juice is evaporated to get thick paste and a small amount of ghee is added to prepare the Beetroot extract. ^[5]

Fig no 2: Aloe vera gel

Fig no 3: Beetroot Extract

- b) **Orange peel powder:** Orange Peel was left out in the sun for few days. Grinded the peel when it has completely dried. Eventually, powder was prepared. It exhibits antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. Orange peel's qualities help tighten the skin by eliminating dead skin cells and absorbing excess oil, while maintaining the natural balance of skin oils. ^[6]

Fig no 4: Orange peel Powder

Fig no 5: Gelatin Powder

- c) ***Aloe barbadensis*:** It was obtained from the Medicinal Garden. Peel off the outer layer of aloe vera and get the pulp. Lastly gel was obtained by grinder. It will aid in the skin's ability to retain moisture. The production of collagen and elastin fibers by aloe promotes fibroblast, which makes the skin less wrinkled, more elastic and soften the skin. ^[7]

Fig no 6: Poly Vinyl Chloride

Method of preparation: [8, 9, 10]

After preparing and weighing all the components, make PVA (distilled water) at 80 °C and prepare gelatine with the same water. Mix the gelatine with PVA before adding it. Add hot distilled water and dissolved citric acid to the mixture. Then, add the herbal extract into a beaker and whirl to incorporate all the ingredients. Distilled water also added until the volume equal to 100% w/w of the entire volume.

Table no. 1 Ingredients list with their quantity.

Sl no	Ingredients	Quantity- F1, F2, F3, F4, F5				
1	Beetroot juice extract	10mg	6mg	10mg	10mg	10mg
2	Orange peel powder	10mg	4mg	Q.S	Q.S	3mg
3	<i>Aloe barbadensis</i>	10mg	4gm	Q.S	Q.S	2mg
4	PVA	3.5g	1.4g	1g	2g	1.6g
5	Gelatine	2g	0.8g	0.5g	1g	0.8g
6	Citric acid	5mg	3mg	4mg	5mg	5mg
7	Water	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S

Evaluation Parameters:

1. **Organoleptic properties** [11, 12]: After visually inspecting the product, we found that,
 - a) Colour:- Pinkish Red
 - b) Odour:- Pleasant odour
 - c) State:- Semi solid
 - d) Consistency:- Smooth

2. **pH** ^[13, 14]: Using a digital pH meter, the pH of this formulation was discovered to be 6.12, as well as the pH of the lip peel-off mask.
3. **Irritancy test** ^[15, 16]: To screen for irritant reactions, such as swelling, itching, and redness on the skin, this formulation was applied to the back of the hand and left on for 15 minutes and observed that there is no irritation.
4. **Spreadability test** ^[17, 18]: Take 1 gm of formulation on butter paper, then placed a watch glass on top of the formulation. The sample was then compressed to a consistent thickness for two minutes using a five-gram weight on a watch glass, after which its diameter was measured.
5. **Peel off test** ^[19, 20]: The formulation film of 4x4mm was spread on backside of the hands skin. Leave it for 15-20 minutes to dry properly. After that, peel off the dry film from the skin surface. Easy removal of peel without any complications was observed.

Fig no 7: Peel off test from hands skin

6. **Folding endurance** ^[21, 22]: Onto the skin was put the formulation film. A section of the film (3 by 3 cm) was cut and folded in the same spot until it broke after drying. A film's folding endurance is determined by how many times it can be folded without breaking.

Fig no 8: Lip Peel off formulation

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

This lip peel off formulation incorporates gelatin as a gelling agent in addition to PVA, which creates a base of gel that can build an elastic film layer that can be readily peeled without splitting or tearing. Beetroot extract contains antioxidants, anti-inflammatory compounds, and vitamin C. It also contains coloring agents such as betanin pigments, which produce a pinkish-red tint.

After applying the mixture, it will dry after 3-4 minutes and peels easily. The Formulation no F1 and F4 has shown the appropriate results. The formulation was made, stored in a dry environment at room temperature and with respect to stability, it was stable for 21 days.

Table no.2 The prepared lip peel off was evaluated and data was reported below.

Sl. No	TESTS	RESULTS
1	Colour	Pinkish orange
2	Odour	Pleasant
3	Consistency	Smooth
4	State	Semi-solid
5	pH	5.75
6	Irritancy test	No irritation effect
7	Spreadability test	Smooth and easy to spread
8	Peel off test	Peel removed from skin easily without breaking
9	Folding endurance	8

CONCLUSION:

Currently, people choose herbal products for their reduced side effects to cure various skin related problems. Herbal ingredients are used to formulate cosmetic products because of their less harmful effects. As compared to synthetic products the herbal products are more preferred by developing countries. This lip peel off is regarded as a long-term and effective method of improving the appearance of the lips.

In the current study, we developed that the formulation is stable at room temperature and has excellent flow characteristics. This formulation exhibited higher comparability and no irritant effects. This formulation has good spreadability and imparts color after peeling. The investigation of this beetroot lip peel off indicated that it is capable of removing dirt and imparting color on the lips, as well as adding like natural color to the lips and protecting them from the outside environment.

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